

DEVELOPMENT OF SINGING SKILLS BY PERFORMING DUTOR IN SINGING STUDENTS

Abdumannatova Aziza Abdumajit kizi,

*Teacher of the Department of “Music Education” of the Samarkand State
Pedagogical Institute, PhD.*

Abstract. *The article analyzes the pedagogical features of developing dutor performance skills in singing students, the inextricable link between singers' vocal and instrumental performance, and the importance of forming accompaniment skills through the dutor. The role of pedagogical approaches, methods, and tools used in the educational process in improving the performance skills of singing students is substantiated.*

Keywords: *dutor instrument, dutor performance, accompaniment, performance skills, singing.*

In the context of educational and cultural integration processes, the content and methodological approaches of music education are being radically updated. In particular, in the process of preparing future music teachers studying in higher pedagogical educational institutions for professional activity, the formation of their performing culture is of great importance. In this regard, for students of the vocal arts department, thorough mastery of instrumental music, in particular the dutor instrument, is manifested not only as a practical but also as a pedagogical necessity.

Today, in the music education system, it is of great importance for students of the singing department to have thorough training not only in vocals, but also in instrumental performance. In particular, mastering the skills of accompaniment through one of our national instruments, the dutor, expands the singer's stage and performance opportunities. Therefore, studying the pedagogical features of developing dutor performance skills in students of the singing department is one of the current pedagogical problems.

The professional training of a student studying in the field of singing should not be limited only to voice capabilities and vocal technique. In the practice of school music education, the teacher simultaneously performs many types of activities, such as singing, playing, independent performance on a musical instrument, working with an ensemble, and analyzing musical works. In this regard, the dutor instrument plays an

important role in the formation of professional competencies of students studying in the field of singing. The dutor has wide opportunities in playing, solo performance, and ensemble performance, and serves to develop students' musical thinking, strengthen their professional knowledge, and improve their artistic taste.

Dutor performance is inextricably linked with singing performance and is an important tool in ensuring the accuracy of song performance and a deep understanding of the character of national melodies and songs. Through the dutor instrument, students learn to feel the basis of the melody, ensure the harmony of voice and instrument, and master the culture of rhythm. This will allow them to organize music lessons in a meaningful, effective, and creative way in their future pedagogical activities.

The direction of singing is aimed at forming the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications in dutor performance among students, in which the integration of traditional and modern pedagogical approaches is important. It is advisable to combine the teacher-student experience inherent in traditional dutor performance schools, national performance styles, ornaments and technical elements formed on the basis of oral tradition with modern teaching methods. In particular, teaching dutor performance through notation, musical analysis, a system of technical exercises, reading from a sheet, and the use of audio and video materials gives good results.

Special attention should be paid to the issues of organizing dutor performance in the process of individual and ensemble training. Individual training serves to develop in the student the correct grip of the instrument, sound production, perfect mastery of right and left hand techniques, and the formation of performance discipline. Ensemble training is aimed at developing the skills of students to hear each other, feel each other, adhere to a common performance culture, and develop the skills of rhythm and harmony. It is especially important to ensure harmony in singing and the dutor ensemble.

The dutor instrument plays an important role in the process of training students in the singing direction. Accompaniment through the dutor ensures the singer's musical hearing, sense of rhythm and pitch, and a deep understanding of the melody and song content. In this process, vocal and instrumental performance develop inextricably. It is important to properly organize the pedagogical process in developing dutor performance skills. First of all, the individual capabilities, level of musical preparation, and vocal characteristics of students should be taken into account. In practical exercises, a gradual transition from simple melody and accompaniment patterns to complex forms gives effective results.

From a pedagogical point of view, the following features are important in teaching dutor performance:

- reliance on national performing traditions and styles;

- development of musical thinking through the performance of vocal works accompanied by dutor;
- use of listening, repetition and independent performance methods in practical exercises;
- formation of stage culture and performance confidence in students.

Also, the process of accompaniment through dutor develops ensemble culture in singers, prepares them for independent creative activity. The methodical approach of the teacher, properly selected exercises and repertoire serve to effectively develop the performing skills of students.

In conclusion, the pedagogical features of developing dutor performance skills in students of the singing department are an important component of the musical education process. The formation of accompaniment skills through the dutor instrument increases the professional skills of the singer, helps to deeply master national musical traditions. The correct selection of pedagogical approaches in this process, special attention to practical exercises, allows achieving high results.

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